

Reactions of isothiocyanates with *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines and benzyloxyamine

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The reactions of α -naphthyl isothiocyanate, allyl isothiocyanate and *n*-propyl isothiocyanate with some *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamine and benzyloxyamine have been investigated.

Although the reactions of isocyanates and isothiocyanates with alcohols, amines and amides have been studied extensively¹, comparatively less work has been reported on their reactions with *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines and alkoxyamine. Cooley *et al.*² studied the reactions of phenyl isocyanate and α -naphthyl isocyanate with some *O*-alkylhydroxamic acids. Reactions of isocyanates and isothiocyanates with *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines and alkoxyamines have been reported by various workers³⁻⁵. The present report includes the reactions of α -naphthyl isothiocyanates, allyl isothiocyanates and *n*-propyl isothiocyanates with some *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines and benzyloxyamine.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines with isothiocyanates were carried out in dry benzene with rigorous exclusion of moisture. The reactions may afford products arising from the attachment of thiocarbamoyl

Scheme 1

group either to nitrogen (**1**) or oxygen (**2**) (Scheme 1).

All the products have been found to have structure **1**.

Like other amines, benzyloxyamine undergoes addition reaction with isothiocyanates, leading to the product **3** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc using benzene-ethyl acetate as eluants. α -Naphthyl isothiocyanate and allyl isothiocyanate (Fluka) were used as received. Propyl isothiocyanate was prepared by the reported method.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL FT-100 instrument using TMS as internal standard. *N*-Acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines^{4,5} and benzyloxyamine² were prepared by reported methods.

Thiocarbamoyl derivatives of *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines. General method : The *N*-aryl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamine (0.005 mol) was stirred with α -naphthyl isothiocyanate (0.005 mol) in dry benzene at 40° for 3 h. On cooling in ice-bath, crystals of the product were obtained.

Thiocarbamoyl derivatives of benzyloxyamine. General method : α -Naphthylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) or allyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added to benzyloxyamine (0.01 mol) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 1 h. It was then ice-cooled and crystallized from C₆H₆-EtOH (1 : 1).

Reaction of N-benzoyl-O-benzylhydroxylamine with α -naphthyl isothiocyanate (1b) : It was a white solid (70%), m.p. 120° (Found : C, 72.78; H, 4.92; N, 6.73; S, 7.74. $C_{25}H_{20}N_2O_2S$ calcd. for : C, 72.82; H, 4.85; N, 6.79; S, 7.76%); ν_{max} 3330 (NH), 1645 (NH-C=O), 1210 (C=S), 840, 760 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 5.0 (2H, m, OCH_2), 7.7–8.3 (17H, m, ArH), 9.8 (1H, m, NH).

Reaction of N-benzoyl-O-butylhydroxylamine with α -naphthyl isothiocyanate (1b) : It was a white solid (40%), m.p. 68°; ν_{max} 3200 (NH), 1645 (NH-C=O), 1200 (C=S), 870, 730 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (3H, t, J 8.0, 6.0 Hz, CH_3), 1.5 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 4.1 (2H, t, J 7.0, 6.0 Hz, OCH_2), 7.0–8.4 (12H, m, ArH), 10.2 (1H, m, NH).

Reaction of N-p-methoxybenzoyl-O-benzylhydroxylamine with propyl isothiocyanate (1c) : It was a white solid (57%), m.p. 70°; ν_{max} 3270 (NH), 1680 (NH-C=O), 1175 (C=S), 760 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.6 (3H, t, J 8.0, 7.0 Hz, CH_3), 1.1 (2H, m, CH_2), 3.2 (2H, m, $NHCH_2$), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.9 (2H, m, OCH_2), 6.7–8.2 (9H, m, ArH), 9.4 (1H, t, J 7.0, 6.0 Hz, NH).

Reaction of benzyloxyamine with α -naphthyl isothiocyanate (3a) : It was a white solid (80%), m.p. 136° (Found : C, 70.10; H, 5.16; N, 8.97; S, 10.42. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2OS$ calcd. for : C, 70.13; H, 5.19; N, 9.09; S, 10.39%); ν_{max} 3370 (NH), 1230 (C=S), 800, 720 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 4.8 (2H, m, OCH_2), 7.0–8.2 (12H, m, ArH), 9.9 (1H, s, NH).

Reaction of benzyloxyamine with allyl isothiocyanate

(3b) : It was a white solid (75%), m.p. 63° (Found : C, 59.37; H, 6.25; N, 12.58; S, 14.39. $C_{11}H_{14}N_2OS$ calcd. for : C, 59.46; H, 6.30; N, 12.61; S, 14.41%); ν_{max} 3360 (NH), 1220 (C=S), 980 ($CH=CH_2$), 720 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.1 (2H, t, J 8.0, 7.0 Hz, CH_2), 4.9 (2H, m, OCH_2), 5.2 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=CH_2$), 5.98 (1H, m, $=CH$), 9.4 (1H, s, NH).

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